

Dr. Bulla Thirumalesh, Lecturer in Economics, Silver Jubilee Government College (A), Kurnool.

Introduction:

Capital market plays an important role in mobilising resources, and diverting them in productive channels. In this way, it facilitates and promotes the process of economic growth in the country. The capital market, as it is known, is that segment of the financial market that deals with the effective channelling of medium to long-term funds from the surplus to the deficit unit. The process of transfer of funds is done through instruments. A capital market is a market for securities (debt or equity), where business enterprises and government can raise long-term funds. It is defined as a market in which money is provided for periods longer than a year, as the raising of short-term funds takes place on other markets (e.g., the money market). The capital market is characterized by a large variety of financial instruments: equity and preference shares, fully convertible debentures (FCDs), non-convertible debentures (NCDs) and partly convertible debentures (PCDs) currently dominate the capital market, however new instruments are being introduced such as debentures bundled with warrants, participating preference shares, zero-coupon bonds, secured premium notes, etc.

Capital market helps in capital formation and economic growth of the country. The capital market acts as an important link between savers and investors. The savers are lenders of funds while investors are borrowers of funds. The savers who do not spend all their income are called. "Surplus units" and the borrowers are known as "deficit units". The capital market is the transmission mechanism between surplus units and deficit units. It is a conduit through which surplus units lend their surplus funds to deficit units. Surplus units buy securities with their surplus funds and deficit units sell securities to raise the funds they need. Funds flow from lenders to borrowers either directly or indirectly through financial institutions such as banks, unit trusts, mutual funds, etc. The borrower's issue primary securities which are purchased by lenders either directly or indirectly through financial institutions.

The capital market encourages economic growth. The various institutions which operate in the capital market give quantities and qualitative direction to the flow of funds and bring rational allocation of resources. They do so by converting financial assets into productive physical assets. This leads to the development of commerce and industry through the private and public sector, thereby inducing economic growth.

Objectives of the study:

The primary objective of the paper is to explain the historical perspective of capital markets and its growth in India. The other objectives of the paper are:

- To explain the Functions and Significance of Capital Market in India.
- To explain the Features of Capital Market and Structure of Indian Capital Market in India.
- To know the Capital Market Reforms in India.

Research Methodology:

Methodology used for this paper is secondary method and the data collected from various secondary resources such as journals, articles and websites.

History of Indian Capital Market:

Initially, East India Company securities were traded in the country. Until the end of the nineteenth century securities trading was unorganized and the main trading centers were Bombay and Calcutta. Trading was at that time limited to a dozen brokers; their trading place was under a banyan tree in front of the Town hall in Bombay. These stock brokers organized informal association in 1897 – Native Shares and Stock Brokers Association, Bombay. The Stock exchanges in Calcutta and Ahmedabad also industrial and trading centers came up later. The Bombay Stock Exchange was recognized in May 1927 under the Bombay Securities Contracts Control Act, 1925.

The capital market was not well organized and developed during the British rule because the British government was not interested in the economic growth of the country. As a result many foreign companies depended on the London capital market for funds rather than in the Indian capital market. In the post-independence period also, the size the capital market remained small. During the first and second five year plans, the government's emphasis was on the development of the agricultural sector and public sector undertakings. The public sector undertakings were healthier than the private undertakings in terms of paid up capital but shares were not listed on the stock exchanges. Moreover, the Controller of Capital Issues (CI) closely supervised and controlled the timing, composition, interest rates pricing allotment and floatation consist of new issues. These strict regulations de-motivated many companies from going public for almost four and a half decades.

The 1990s will go down as the most important decade in the history of the capital market of India. Liberalisation and globalization were the new terms coined and marketed during the decade this decade. The Capital Issues (Control) Act, 1947 was repealed in May 1992. The decade was characterized by a new industrial policy, emergence of SEBI as a regulator of capital market, advent of foreign institutional investors, euro-issues, free pricing, new trading practices, new stock exchanges, entry of new players such as private sector mutual funds and private sector banks, and primary market boom and bust.¹² Major capital market scams took place in the 1990s. These shook the capital market and drove away small investors from the market. The securities scam of March, 1992 involving brokers as well as bankers was one of the biggest scams in the history of the capital market. In the subsequent years owing to free pricing, many unscrupulous promoters, who raised money from the capital market, proved to be fly-by-night operators. This led to an erosion in the investors' confidence. The 1991-1992 securities scam revealed the inadequacies of and inefficiencies in the financial system. It was the scam, which prompted a reform of the equity market. The Indian stock market witnessed a sea change in terms of technology and market prices. Technology brought radical changes in the trading mechanism.

The Indian capital market entered the twenty-first century with the Ketan Paresh scam. As a result of this scam, badla was discontinued from July 2001 and rolling settlement was introduced in all scrips. Trading of futures commenced from June 2000, and Internet trading was permitted in February 2000. On July 2, 2001, the Unit Trust of India announced suspension of the sale and repurchase of its flagship US-64 scheme due to heavy redemption leading to panic on the bourses. The government's decision to privatize oil PSUs in 2003 fuelled stock prices. One big divestment of international telephony major VSNL took place in early February 2002. Foreign institutional investors have emerged as major players on the Indian bourses. NSE has an upper hand over its rival BSE in terms of volumes not only in the equity markets but also in the derivatives market. It has been a long journey for the Indian capital market.

Functions and Significance of Capital Market:

The capital market plays an important role immobilizing saving and channel is in them into productive investments for the development of commerce and industry. As such, the capital market helps in capital formation and economic growth of the country. Various functions and significance of capital market are discussed below:

1. Encouragement to Investment:

The capital market facilitates lending to the businessmen and the government and thus encourages investment. It provides facilities through banks and nonbank financial institutions. Various financial assets, *e.g.*, shares, securities, bonds, etc., induce savers to lend to the government or invest in industry. With the development of financial institutions, capital becomes more mobile, interest rate falls and investment increases.

2. Encouragement to Saving:

With the development of capital, market, the banking and non-banking institutions provide facilities, which encourage people to save more. In the less- developed countries, in the absence of a capital market, there are very little savings and those who save often invest their savings in unproductive

and wasteful directions, i.e., in real estate (like land, gold, and jewellery) and conspicuous consumption.

3. Promotes Economic Growth:

The capital market not only reflects the general condition of the economy, but also smoothens and accelerates the process of economic growth. Various institutions of the capital market, like nonbank financial intermediaries, allocate the resources rationally in accordance with the development needs of the country.

4. Link between Savers and Investors:

The capital market functions as a link between savers and investors. It plays an important role in mobilising the savings and diverting them in productive investment. In this way, capital market plays a vital role in transferring the financial resources from surplus and wasteful areas to deficit and productive areas, thus increasing the productivity and prosperity of the country.

5. Stability in Security Prices:

The capital market tends to stabilise the values of stocks and securities and reduce the fluctuations in the prices to the minimum. The process of stabilisation is facilitated by providing capital to the borrowers at a lower interest rate and reducing the speculative and unproductive activities.

Features of Capital Market:

1. Deals in Long Term Investment: Capital market provides funds for long and medium term. It does not deal with channelising saving for less than one year.

2. Determinant of Capital Formation: The activities of capital market determine the rate of capital formation in an economy. Capital market offers attractive opportunities to those who have surplus funds so that they invest more and more in capital market and are encouraged to save more for profitable opportunities.

3. Utilises Intermediaries: Capital market makes use of different intermediaries such as brokers, underwriters, depositories etc. These intermediaries act as working organs of capital market and are very important elements of capital market.

4. Government Rules and Regulations: The capital market operates freely but under the guidance of government policies. These markets function within the framework of government rules and regulations, e.g., stock exchange works under the regulations of SEBI which is a government body.

5. Link between Savers and Investment Opportunities: Capital market is a crucial link between saving and investment process. The capital market transfers money from savers to entrepreneurial borrowers.

Structure of Indian Capital Market:

Broadly speaking the capital market is classified in to two categories. They are the Primary market (New Issues Market) and the Secondary market (Old (Existing) Issues Market). This classification is done on the basis of the nature of the instrument brought in the market. However, on the basis of the types of institutions involved in capital market, it can be classified into various categories such as the Government Securities market or Gilt-edged market, Industrial Securities market, Development Financial Institutions (DFIs) and financial intermediaries. All of these components have specific features to mention. The structure of the Indian capital market has its distinct features. These different segments of the capital market help to develop the institution of capital market in many dimensions. The primary market helps to raise fresh capital in the market. In the secondary market, the buying and selling (trading) of capital market instruments takes place. The following chart will help us in understanding the organizational structure of the Indian Capital market.

- 1) **Government Securities Market:** This is also known as the Gilt-edged market. This refers to the market for government and semi-government securities backed by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI).
- 2) **Industrial Securities Market:** This is a market for industrial securities i.e. market for shares and debentures of the existing and new corporate firms. Buying and selling of such instruments take place in this market. This market is further classified into two types such as the New Issues Market (Primary) and the Old (Existing) Issues Market (secondary). In primary market fresh capital is raised by companies by issuing new shares, bonds, units of mutual funds and debentures. However in the secondary market already existing i.e old shares and debentures are traded. This trading takes place through the registered stock exchanges. In India we have three prominent stock exchanges. They are the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE), the National Stock Exchange (NSE) and Over the Counter Exchange of India (OTCEI).
- 3) **Development Financial Institutions (DFIs):** This is yet another important segment of Indian capital market. This comprises various financial institutions. These can be special purpose institutions like IFCI, ICICI, SFCs, IDBI, IIBI, UTI, etc. These financial institutions provide long term finance for those purposes for which they are set up.
- 4) **Financial Intermediaries:** The fourth important segment of the Indian capital market is the financial intermediaries. This comprises various merchant banking institutions, mutual funds, leasing finance companies, venture capital companies and other financial institutions. These are important institutions and segments in the Indian capital market.

Capital Market Reforms in India:

Role of capital market in economic progress of a country is significant and essential. The record of capital market operations can be traced around middle of 19th century in india. But till very recently, nothing is done towards the development of Indian Capital Market. The following are some of the reforms which brought drastic changes in Indian capital market.

1. **Establishment of SEBI India:** The Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) was established in 1988. It got a legal status in 1992. SEBI was primarily set up to regulate the activities of the merchant banks, to control the operations of mutual funds, to work as a

- promoter of the stock exchange activities and to act as a regulatory authority of new issue activities of companies.
2. **Establishment of Creditors Rating Agencies:** Three creditors rating agencies viz. The Credit Rating Information Services of India Limited (CRISIL - 1988), the Investment Information and Credit Rating Agency of India Limited (ICRA - 1991) and Credit Analysis and Research Limited (CARE) were set up in order to assess the financial health of different financial institutions and agencies related to the stock market activities. It is a guide for the investors also in evaluating the risk of their investments.
 3. **Increasing of Merchant Banking Activities:** Many Indian and foreign commercial banks have set up their merchant banking divisions in the last few years. These divisions provide financial services such as underwriting facilities, issue organizing, consultancy services, etc. It has proved as a helping hand to factors related to the capital market.
 4. **Rising Electronic Transactions:** Due to technological development in the last few years. The physical transaction with more paper work is reduced. Now paperless transactions are increasing at a rapid rate. It saves money, time and energy of investors. Thus it has made investing safer and hassle free encouraging more people to join the capital market.
 5. **Growing Mutual Fund Industry:** The growing of mutual funds in India has certainly helped the capital market to grow. Public sector banks, foreign banks, financial institutions and joint mutual funds between the Indian and foreign firms have launched many new funds. A big diversification in terms of schemes, maturity, etc. has taken place in mutual funds in India. It has given a wide choice for the common investors to enter the capital market.
 6. **Growing Stock Exchanges:** The numbers of various Stock Exchanges in India are increasing. Initially the BSE was the main exchange, but now after the setting up of the NSE, stock exchanges have spread across the country. Recently a new Inter-connected Stock Exchange of India has joined the existing stock exchanges.
 7. **Investors Protection:** Under the preview of the SEBI the Central Government of India has set up the Investors Education and Protection Fund (IEPF) in 2001. It works in educating and guiding investors. It tries to protect the interest of the small investors from frauds and malpractices in the capital market
 8. **Growth of Derivative Transactions:** Since June 2000, the NSE has introduced the derivatives trading in the equities. In November 2001 it also introduced the future and options transactions. These innovative products have given variety for the investment leading to the expansion of the capital market.
 9. **Insurance Sector Reforms:** Indian insurance sector has also witnessed massive reforms in last few years. The Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA) was set up in 2000. It paved the entry of the private insurance firms in India. As many insurance companies invest their money in the capital market, it has expanded.
 10. **Commodity Trading:** Along with the trading of ordinary securities, the trading in commodities is also recently encouraged. The Multi Commodity Exchange (MCX) is set up. The volume of such transactions is growing at a splendid rate. Apart from these reforms the setting up of Clearing Corporation of India Limited (CCIL), Venture Funds, etc., have resulted into the tremendous growth of Indian capital market. Reference
 11. **Depositories Act:** Depositories Act 1996 is passed to provide a legal framework for the establishment of depositories to record ownership details in book entry form. It also facilitates dematerialization of securities.

Conclusion:

The capital market was not well organized and developed during the British rule because the British government was not interested in the economic growth of the country. As a result many foreign companies depended on the London capital market for funds rather than in the Indian capital market. In the post-independence period also, the size the capital market remained small. During the first and second five-year plans, the government's emphasis was on the development of the

agricultural sector and public sector undertakings. The public sector undertakings were healthier than the private undertakings in terms of paid-up capital but shares were not listed on the stock exchanges. Moreover, the Controller of Capital Issues (CI) closely supervised and controlled the timing, composition; interest rates pricing allotment and floatation consist of new issues. These strict regulations de-motivated many companies from going public for almost four and a half decades. Now the capital market is organized, fairly integrated, mature, more global and modernized. The Indian equity market is one of the best in the world in terms of technology. Advances in computer and communications technology coming together on Internet are shattering geographic boundaries and enlarging the investor class. Internet trading has become a global phenomenon. The Indian stock markets are now getting integrated with global markets. The capital market plays an important role immobilizing saving and channel is in them into productive investments for the development of commerce and industry. As such, the capital market helps in capital formation and economic growth of the country. The capital market encourages economic growth. The various institutions which operate in the capital market give quantities and qualitative direction to the flow of funds and bring rational allocation of resources. They do so by converting financial assets into productive physical assets. This leads to the development of commerce and industry through the private and public sector, thereby inducing economic growth. With the entry of mutual funds, the capital market became very active and its turnover increased drastically after introduction of reforms.

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